

Enhancing Pakistani Undergraduate ESL University Students' Reading Comprehension Through the Use of Cooperative Learning Techniques

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DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Keywords:

ESL Students, Reading Comprehension, Cooperative Learning Techniques

Article History

Received on 22 Oct 2025

Accepted on 20 Nov 2025

Published on 02 Dec 2025

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Abstract

The present study investigates the effect of cooperative learning techniques on Pakistani undergraduate ESL (BS) 1st semester university students at a public sector university Karachi. The Quasi-experimental design was used with two groups (experimental and control group) of 40 participants each to investigate the impact of cooperative learning techniques on students' reading comprehension skills. The experimental group was taught through cooperative learning techniques whereas the control group was taught through traditional teaching technique. Moreover, this treatment lasted for 14 weeks. The result shows that the students of the experimental group scored higher in reading comprehension skills in their post-test after the treatment of cooperative learning techniques. Thus, it is recommended that cooperative learning techniques should be adopted to the undergraduate students to improve their reading comprehension skills.

INTRODUCTION

The present study investigates the effect of the Cooperative learning techniques on Pakistani undergraduate ESL university students' reading comprehension in the Pakistani context. A quasi-experimental design has been used along with pretest and post-test to examine the effect of the Cooperative learning techniques on university undergraduate ESL students' reading comprehension in the Pakistani context.

Background of the Study

This section presents the background of the study and gives the context in which the study has been done.

Importance of English Language

Globally, English has achieved the most prominent and prestigious status which is formally spoken and taught in all the educational and official systems. The four English language abilities of writing, reading, speaking, and listening must all be mastered by learners. In addition, reading and listening are the raw materials of writing and speaking respectively. Therefore, writing and speaking are deemed to be the productive or proficiencies, while reading and listening are considered to be receptive or passive proficiencies (Namaziandost et al., 2020). So it simply means that the more one reads and listens the more one is able to communicate and write well. It goes without saying that learning a second or foreign language is necessary if you want to be able to communicate in that tongue. Therefore, learning English is necessary in order to communicate with people around the world (Homayouni et al., 2020). In order to achieve both academic and outcome success, students are required to get and increase their knowledge. However, to get the knowledge

they are needed to be well versed in all the four abilities of English.

In addition, all the four competencies of English language are interlinked to each other. Whether it is in a professional field or academic systems all the competencies such as writing, reading, speaking and listening are necessary to be acquired. In the USA, roundabout 9.4% of public school's students are learning English language and most of these students are associated with different institutions in order to enhance their language proficiencies (McFarland et al., 2017). Since English language has spread across the world, it has become the lingua franca (ELF); bringing people near to each other belonging to different cultures and castes (Fan, 2017). English is not only used at international level but it is also used in multilingual societies as a language of interaction. Additionally, English now serves as a global lingua franca and is no longer the language of the inner circle of nations (McKay, 2002). As per many well-known scholars, English is highly in demand among the people because it is the language of many professions such as entertainment, services, trade, media, and science (Crystal, 1997). English has become the language of inter and intra- cultural communications (Crystal, 2003).

Status of English Language in Pakistan

It is perceived that in Pakistan approximately 72 languages are spoken such as Urdu, English, Pashto, Sindhu, Balochi and Punjabi (Rehman, 1998). However, Urdu and English reserve the status of being national and official languages respectively (Rehman, 1998). In Pakistan English doesn't only preserve the status of being official language but also works as a medium of interaction among the government institutions (Hind et al., 2020). In Pakistan, English is the language of the upper class because they not only use it

for their communication purposes but also use it for official and unofficial matters (Zaman, Chandio, and Noor (2025). It has now become the most important part of Pakistani society and is liked by a vast amount of people. Pakistan having more than 200 million populations, is considered to be as much an English speaking country as Urdu speaking (Rehman, 1998). The variety of English, which is written and spoken in Pakistan is called Pakistani English (Baumgardner, 1987; Rahman et al., 1990). In accent and pronunciation, Pakistani English is unlike that of American and British English (Rahman, 1990). English is a required subject in the Pakistani educational system beginning in either class 1 or class 6. (Rahman, 2010). Furthermore, English functions as a medium of interaction among the students in most of the Pakistani schools and not only this have had they also used it as a language of interaction at their homes (Rahman, 1998).

In addition, English is the language of army, bureaucracy, judiciary and parliament. However, parliament also permits Urdu to be used for parliamentary purposes but the records are all written in English (Rahman, 2009). The reason that English preserves official status in Pakistan is because it is used in all higher and prestigious institutions of the country such as army, bureaucracy, judiciary and parliament. Though, English is the official language of Pakistan still it cannot be spoken by most of the people as a first language but it is learnt as a second language for so many other objectives such as education, business, and travelling abroad (Ahmed et al., 2013).

Pakistani Students' ESL Reading Skills

Unfortunately, Pakistan has never done a significant work in the Pakistani educational institutions such as, the engineering students are not competent at reading comprehension

because they are introduced to two different systems of education (public education system/ private education system) where in private education system the Syllabus is taught in English whereas in public educational system Syllabus is taught in Urdu which causes poor reading comprehension of the students (Nawab, 2012; Mahboob et al., 2017). Apart from this there are many other elements which are the cause of weak language skills of students' especially reading comprehension (Kakepoto et al., 2012). In Pakistan many students are not capable of taking an active part in reading comprehension strategies because of lack of knowledge of such techniques, that's why they get flocked in getting maximum advantages from the activities which are done out in the classes and also to utilize them outside of the class setting (Haq, 2016). Despite using the latest reading strategies, teachers are stuck to the old traditional method of memorization in order to make ready students for the exams (Khan, 2007). Moreover, students in Pakistan cannot utilize their analytical and cognitive abilities in order to process the needed information from the lengthy text by themselves just because they are not prepared and trained. Therefore, this results in a weak execution process of reading English at a higher level (Mumtaz, 2006). Just because the students' core motive is to pass the examination therefore they don't show much interest in using reading techniques (Kasi, 2010). In addition, the main reading strategies which are used by Pakistani students are only reading for information, summarizing the text, reading aloud and answering the questions for comprehension (Gulzar & Qadir, 2010). Ahmad (1979) claims that in Pakistan, teachers are unable to execute the reading strategies at secondary level as per the requirement of the interest of students. Shahzada (2002) states that,

however, in Pakistan students employ various reading methodologies but still their overall reading skills are not up to the mark.

Reading, however, is supposed to be the most challenging task as compared to the rest of the other three abilities that's why the matric students' low level academic achievement and failure in the exams are the mere consequences of their poor ability of reading comprehension (Mbocha, 2015). Both, reading fluency and comprehension are keys to learn. Therefore, students having troubles in reading comprehension usually have low motivation towards learning which consequently leave bad impact over their academic learning (Allington, 2013). In the USA, roundabout 9.4% of public schools students are learning English language and most of these students are associated with different institutions in order to enhance their reading proficiencies (McFarland et al., 2017). In spite of that much English language students, enrolled in secondary level, have hindrances in reading comprehension (National Centre for Education Statistics [NCES], 2016). EL (English learners) students, who are getting special training on reading comprehension, are performing badly as compared to the EL students who are not associated with any special institutions (NCES, 2016). Just because English is a doorway to all opportunities either at national level or international level, therefore, in Taiwan universities students are motivated to pass the English language assessment at graduation level. Students in Taiwan universities, however, encounter a lot of problems in reading comprehension (Yang, 2012).

Collaborative Learning Activities for Teaching Reading

In academic classes, the way other skills are taught through traditional approach rather

than any other unusual way, the same way reading comprehension is also enhanced through traditional ways (Namaziandost, Hosseini et al., 2020). In traditional way of teaching, the reading teacher teaches the text to the students and in the end the teacher asks questions from the students in order to know whether students get the text or not. On the other hand, students try to compete with each other to respond correctly to the teacher's questions (Allington, 2013). However, students who cannot answer the questions correctly get disappointed, despite putting in a huge amount of time and energy, satisfactory results are not obtained (Allington, 2013). In this regard, new methods and strategies are needed to be introduced in the class and in this regard enhancing reading comprehension through Cooperative learning strategies has proven to be the most significant method (Yang, 2012). Moreover, Tyner (2014) suggests that by introducing latest technologies and strategies can help students to upgrade their reading comprehension more effectively rather than the old traditional ways. In EFL context, applying Cooperative learning strategies have a sole purpose to develop reading comprehension of the students (Richards & Schmidt 2010).

No doubt, there are many well-known Cooperative learning techniques but Jigsaw technique is one of the most prominent techniques which is used in collaborative learning environments (Jaccob, 1998). Through Jigsaw technique students in the class are divided in the small groups, then these small groups are given the same topic and then that topic is divided into further subtopics and are assigned to each member of the groups (Jaccob, 1998). In jigsaw technique students learn by means of activities in which they collaborate with each other to obtain their goals (Haryanto 2012). In the jigsaw classes, students were found more

regular, confident and liked the school environment when they were assessed objectively (Francis 2013). Having analyzed the collected data, it showed that jigsaw technique was more influential as compared to the traditional way of teaching (Sabah 2016).

Statement of the Problem

Globally, English has got the most prominent and prestigious status, therefore, it is formally spoken and taught in all the educational and official systems (McNamara & Magliano, 2009). Learners are required to be proficient in all the four skills of the English language, such as reading, writing, speaking and listening (Perfetti & Stafura, 2014). In addition, reading and listening are the raw materials of writing and speaking respectively (Perfetti & Stafura, 2014). Therefore, writing and speaking are deemed to be the productive or active proficiencies, while reading and listening are considered to be passive or receptive proficiencies (Croxley et al., 2010). Reading is a highly complicated phenomenon in which linguistics and optical systems interact with each other (Liversedge et al., 2011). According to Perfetti & Adlof (2012) reading is a complex process of creating meaning from the written symbols with the help of various interrelated information. (McMaster, & Christ, 2016) explained reading as "the meaning of constructing and extraction phenomena via the involvement and interaction with written signs.

Reading comprehension means to construct and develop correct meaning of the reading materials with the help of the text and readers' prior knowledge (Gani, Yusuf, Susiani, Gani, and Yusuf, 2016). Reading comprehension, however, is perceived to be the most challenging task as compared to the rest of the other language abilities (Berardo, 2006). Therefore, students having troubles in reading

comprehension usually have low motivation towards learning which consequently leaves a bad impact on their academic learning (Allington, 2013).

Having not enough knowledge of the cooperative learning techniques, Pakistani students cannot take part in an active manner in reading techniques. Therefore, they are unable to get maximum advantages of reading related activities taking place in the classroom and to implement them in the productively outside of classroom (Haq, 2016). Instead of using latest teaching related strategies, teachers are bent to utilize the old techniques of memorizations in order to prepare students for examinations (Khan, 2007). Have not been prepared and trained, Pakistani students are not able to utilize analytical and cognitive capabilities to process the required needed information from longer text passages. Hence, it causes poor English reading performance at the level of university (Mumtaz, 2006).

Moreover, Tyner (2014) suggests that introducing the latest techniques and strategies, can help students to upgrade their reading comprehension more effectively rather than the old traditional ways. Many researchers have indicated that cooperative learning strategies obtain more achievement, self-esteem and interpersonal relationships rather than the old traditional procedure (Hosseini et al., 2020). It has proven that when students learn reading comprehension through Cooperative learning technique, enormous amounts of positive results are obtained which consequently lead the students to understand the text well (Shatalebi et al., 2019). Adams (2013) emphasizes the similar idea that it is necessary to bring new teaching methodologies in classroom environments to derail the students from the old fashion of memorization of the text.

Therefore, the researcher wants to conduct a study to explore the outcome of the

Collaborative learning techniques on Pakistani undergraduate ESL university students' reading comprehension in the Pakistani context.

Research Objectives

The research has the following research objective:

To find out the effect of cooperative learning techniques on Pakistani undergraduate ESL university students' reading comprehension skills

Research Question

The following are research questions;
What is the effect of cooperative learning techniques on Pakistani ESL undergraduate university students' reading comprehension skills?

Scope of the Study

This study explored the effect of only two Cooperative learning techniques on Pakistani ESL undergraduate university students' reading comprehension skills.

For this study, the data were collected from one Pakistani public sector university only.

For the present study, the data were collected through reading test only.

The data for this study were collected during the months of December 2021 to February 2022 only

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it tries to fill the gap in the literature by exploring the effect of the Cooperative learning techniques on reading comprehension of Pakistani undergraduate ESL university students in the Pakistani setting.

The outcomes of the present study be able to be helpful for the Pakistani ESL teachers as they will be able to improve the followings: First of all, it will be beneficial for ESL

students in enhancing their reading comprehension. Moreover, it will help English language teachers to guide their students to enhance their reading competency through the utilization of Cooperative learning techniques such as, Jigsaw technique and Think-pair-share technique. Lastly, it will produce good readers in the society who can apply their knowledge for the betterment and progress of the society.

This study may prove to be the catalyst for further research in the Pakistani context on this topic.

Review of the Related Literature

Reading:

Looking at a series of written symbols in order to get the meaning is called reading (Hempenstal, 2013). For reading we utilize our eyes to understand the written symbols and then we utilize our brain in order to convert that symbols into words that convey something to us (Shaywitz, 2005). Reading is a highly complicated phenomenon in which linguistics and optical systems interact with each other (Liversedge, Gilchrist, & Everling, 2011). According to (BNR, 1985) a complex process of creating meaning from the written symbols with the help of various interrelated information (Rand, 2002) explained reading as "the meaning constructing and extraction phenomena via the involvement and interaction with written signs. (Purcell-Gates, Duke & Stouffer, 2016) defined as "reading is a process that happens in the context of literacy practices which are constructed sociocultural. Reading is a process which occurs in the specially practiced context that is the amalgamation of listening, writing, speaking along with reading itself (Street, 2005). Moreover, reading fluency is the comprehension of the written material as well as the correct identification of the written symbols (Pikulski & Chard, 2005). Further,

(Rasinski et al., 2015) stated that the identification of words depends on reading the words with speed and accuracy while comprehension depends on the prosody of the words.

Definition

Reading is a kind of process in which symbols are decoded cognitively in order to get its meaning (Asprani, 2019). Reading is a kind of process in which the meanings of words are constructed (Jalal, 2020). From a reader, context, and text perspective, reading comprehension is one of the most difficult abilities to master (Sanora, 2022).

Process of Reading:

Reading is a type of cognitive function that involves word recognition and is essential for text comprehension (Sumiati et al., 2019). According to studies, reading is a phenomenon where the reader and the text's meaning interact, and this process entails three steps (Hafsha, 2020). The very first step is pre-reading which is supposed to activate the prior knowledge of the reader regarding the text and therefore it helps the reader to build up the purpose of reading (Han, 2018). The reader must amass all background information pertaining to the essential terms in the text's title in order to effectively complete this step (Miyane, 2020).

Purpose of Reading:

The core purpose of reading is to connect your prior knowledge about a particular topic to the written symbols on the topic. However, if you are still trying to pour the text into your brain while being unable to connect it to your prior understanding of the subject, it will be like someone pouring water into their hands and being unable to retain anything (Shih, 1992). If you like cricket then the process of reading about cricket is more easy and

entertaining (Casanave, 1988). The reader has a framework in his mind for reading which is understanding the text and storing the necessary information that's why it improves a reader's reading comprehension (Li, 2018). With respect to this, reading comprehension involves good study strategies, cognitive frameworks for retaining ideas, motivation and concentration (Miller & Perkins, 1990)

Significance of Reading:

Since reading is the most important process for enhancing one's knowledge therefore it can be useful while getting prepared for examinations (Bijani & Hashempour, 2021). However, being an incumbent part of our education organization, some integral skills are built up with the help of extensive reading which is deemed to be beneficial for the preparation of competitive examinations in the future (Choe, 2017). Moreover, there are some advantages which can be acquired by reading such as, enhancing vocabulary, getting meaning of the written text, containing stories and information, learning new words, coming across the new civilization and cultures of various regions in the world by the help of literature (Mansur, 2019).

Reading Comprehension

By using the text and the readers' prior knowledge to construct and develop the proper meaning of the reading materials (Namaziandost et al., 2020). Reading comprehension, however, is perceived to be the most challenging task as compared to the rest of the other language abilities (Namaziandost et al., 2020). The matric students' low level academic achievement and failure in the exams are the mere consequences of their poor ability of reading comprehension (Mbocha 2015). Both, reading fluency and comprehension are keys to learn. Therefore, students having troubles in reading

comprehension usually have low motivation towards learning which consequently leave bad impact on their academic learning (Allington, 2013).

Types of Reading

Reading is as important to the mind as exercise is important to the body, therefore, no other comparison can be found because the way you are required to do physical exercise to strengthen your body the same way the mind also needs some exercise and that is reading (Almutairi 2018).

Reading is intended for a variety of purposes, including enjoyment, finding the answers to questions, and cleansing the mind. May you read for any purpose but it helps a lot in activating the mind and enhancing speaking skills as well, which is beneficial for doing well in a professional field (Nikmah, 2020). Just as in all the different fields in the world having various simple and specialized equipment the same way reading also has various types of reading methodologies (Dwigustini & Widiya, 2020). It is indispensable to know the different types of readings before you start reading in order to get yourself benefited maximally (Sumekto, 2018). Reading can be for any reason such as for pleasure, for passing time, for academic purpose or any other purpose but you have to be familiar with all the types of readings (Agussatriana, 2020).

Academic Reading

Reading specifically for educational or academic purposes is called academic reading (Maulidiyah & Wahyuningsih, 2019). Academic reading is meant to read materials including, encyclopedias, traditional books, journals articles, dictionaries and a huge amount of material which is available on the internet (Vidya & Nuraini, 2019). This type of reading is solely for the academic purpose in

which it deals with the reflection of the relationship between different parts of reading material, connecting the text you are reading now to the other related text, interpreting the text and making clear your topic and the purpose of reading (Vidya & Nuraini, 2019). Therefore, reading for academic purposes requires more probing, active and recursive methods as compared to that of reading for recreation (Mu'in et al., 2020).

Extensive Reading

Extensive reading is meant to be done for pleasure, entertainment or time pass (Mihara, 2011). When a reader wants to savor the reading experience, they should use extensive reading (Suardi et al., 2020). It is a kind of reading method which puts no pressure or burden on the reader because the reader has no other compulsion except doing it for pleasure (Suardi et al., 2020). This type of reading happens naturally just like a child reads who has no burden as reader at that point of moment (Miyane, 2020). Extensive reading is supposed to be performed casually which is to either get general understanding or pleasure may it be of any kind of reading material such as a book, newspaper and magazine (Mihara, 2011).

Intensive Reading

Out of all the various reading types intensive reading is employed when the objective of reading is to understand the text fully word by word (Van Rhyn & Van Staden, 2018). Prior to exams students use extensive reading to decipher every unfamiliar word or any expression (Paribakht & Wesche, 1993). Intensive reading makes the students retain the specific information for a long period of time (Li, 2018). Intensive reading is considered to be a type of reading in which the reader reads any particular text very deeply and closely with the purpose of

achieving its linguistic and literary meaning (Miller & Perkins, 1990). The readers are required to read the text very intimately, with due care and intensively as it has some learning tasks and objectives (Sakaeva & Ismagilova, 2017).

Reading for Scanning

Scanning reading is one of the various types of reading in which the reader's aim is to look for a particular information and in this regard the reader skim over the text unless he finds the particular information (Perkins, 1988). Scanning is just like when you visit a museum and your purpose is to see the painting of Mona Lisa and then quickly go through all the rooms and the corridor of the museum until you find the painting of Mona Lisa, therefore scanning is exactly like searching Mona Lisa in the museum (Chandran & Shah, 2019). This type of reading is employed when one is not required to read the text in depth but just has to find out the particular information which he has to answer to any question (Sabbah, 2016).

Reading for Skimming

Reading for skimming is a reading technique where the reader must quickly comprehend the entirety of the material, which requires the reader to quickly scan the text (Bijani & Hashempour, 2021). Skimming is a very useful way to understand the themes and motives of any text in a general way and also this way is used to confirm whether the information is beneficial or not (Huda, 2019). Magazine is the best example of skimming in which the reader flips through it in order to get the broad concept of what has been written in that (Huda, 2019).

Models of Reading

Researchers have been looking for a connection between teaching methods and the

reading process for the past 40 years. They have created a reading model that reflects how they perceive and understand the reading process. As per Singer and Ruddell (1985) point of view, a reading model is a sort of graphical activity "to show how a reader comprehends a clause, a word and perceives the written text. However, there are various reading models but only three of them are very popular among the readers and researchers such as "Top-down, Bottom-up, and Interactive".

Top-down Reading Model

Top-down reading model is considered to be a reading model which insists on theory that readers don't take meaning from the text but they themselves bring meanings to the text. Dechant (1991) claims that, from the perspective of a top-down reading model, Readers must simply recognize the words and letters in the text in order to confirm their assumptions about its meaning. Reading is a process where the readers must infuse meaning into the text rather than deriving it from the print (McCormick, T. 1988). Reading is not about to decode the written text to spoken language (Frank Smith, 1989). Top-down reading model utilizes the text as input and the meaning which is extracted from the text as output (Goodman, K. 1981).

Bottom-up Reading Model

The second reading model is bottom-up reading model which focuses on extraction of meaning from the text where readers draw out meaning from the text. Bottom-up reading model doesn't give focus on the reader's contextual information, world knowledge and other strategies (Dechant 1991). Readers are required to know how to convey the signals of auditory language to that of language of visual signs (Fries 1962). The goal of learning to read is to acquire a sufficient number of

automatic responses to a specific set of printed text patterns (Fries 1962).

Interactive Reading Model

The third reading model is known as collaborating reading model which is the combination of both top-down and bottom-up reading models therefore it recognizes both the reading models on the process of reading. In order to avoid the criticism of the other two models it employs the strong points from both the models to make it an excellent approach (McCormick, T. 1988).

Challenges in Developing ESL Reading Skills

Majority of students are of the opinion that English language is more complicated and difficult as compared to other languages but not only this they also believe that specifically reading comprehension is more toxic and boring which discourages and motivates them to comprehend the English text (Susilawati, 2010). Unfortunately, the traditional way of teaching doesn't teach strategies and skills to the students which are indispensable for the students to comprehend the text (Tivanan & Hemphill, 2005). Due to the problem of phonological coding and also capability of translating letter patterns into phonological patterns most of the students face difficulties especially in reading words (Mahapatra, 2016). Many researches related to this field have shown that the reason of poor reading skills of second language students is the deficit of syntactic, awareness of phonology and semantics skills in their mother tongue (Ganschow & Sparks, 1995; Sparks, Patton, Ganschow, Humbach & Javorsky, 2006). While reading comprehension is difficult even in one's own native language therefore it becomes more complicated and difficult in second language (Wickramaarachchi, 2017).

Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning is a sort of way of learning which takes place in a group (Nikmah, 2020). That's why it is also called collaborative learning and it's also the core focus of this study (Nikmah, 2020). Moreover, in this kind of study students make various groups and study to achieve the assigned goal (Dwiniasih & Nugraha, 2019). Each member of the group is responsible for his own section but in general they work for the whole group. In this kind of study students work face to face and work as a team. Cooperative learning is regarded the best way of working together and achieving the goal which is not possible alone (Johnson et al., 1986). The purpose of this sort of approach is to make students creative and make them able to analyze as well as apply concepts (Kagan, 1990). It has been proved if students work together the ratio of achievement is more than that of students who work alone and thus leading to a more comprehensible achievement (Morrow & Sharkey, 1993). Cooperative learning is a type of group based activity which is supposed to bring students together in order to solve various problems related to their study (Morrow & Sharkey, 1993). There is a clear evidence which shows that whenever students debate and discuss any text material in a collaborative and Cooperative way the result is always positive and gets greater understanding (Namaziandost et al., 2019). However, the Cooperative learning approach was started in America in 1970, in order to enable students to achieve their goals in classrooms (Kessler, 1992). According to D.W Johnson (1989), Cooperative learning technique is supposed to be a teaching methodology in which people of different abilities come together and work in a team in order to improve their understanding of the topic. It is found by many researchers that Cooperative learning approach gets more

achievement, self-esteem and interpersonal relationship as compared to individualistic and aggressive approach (Gomleksiz, 2007; Namaziandost, Hosseini et al., 2020).

History of Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning technique approach was started in America in 1970, in order to enable students to achieve their goals in classrooms (Kessler, 1992). Before world war 2, some very renowned social theorists such as Shaw, Allport, Mead and Watson started establishing a collaborative learning theory after knowing that Cooperative work or group work was more efficient and effective in quality, quantity and overall a very beneficial than working individually (Afif Razali et al., 2019). However, in 1937 two very popular researchers such as Doob and May found that those people who work in collaboration are able to achieve better results as compared to those who work independently to achieve the same goals (Apriani, 2019). Those who work cooperatively are likely to have more probability of showing competitive behaviours (JALAL, 2020). Moreover, the greatest philosophers in 1930 and 1940 such as Morton Deutsch, Kurt Lewin and John Dewey also endorsed Cooperative learning techniques which are employed today (Sanora, 2022). Lewin had a great contribution to cooperative learning technique for giving the ideas that group members working in a collaboration are more likely to achieve and carry out the goals successfully (Suardi et al., 2020). However, the contribution of Deutsch to Cooperative learning technique was socially positive and interdependent because he had the idea that each individual is responsible for contributing in a group work (Maryati & Sari, 2021). In addition, Roger Johnson and David have also contributed enormously to the theory of cooperative learning technique (Baskin &

Shitai, 1996). In this regard, in 1975 they discovered that collaborative learning encouraged common liking, great support and acceptance, and good communication showed a huge increase in a multiplicity of thinking methods among members in the group (Hafsha, 2020). Individuals who demonstrated to be more efficient, however, lacked in their trust and interaction with others and their emotional involvement with others was also not up to the mark (Han, 2018).

Principles of CL

However, till date many Cooperative learning techniques have been suggested by different intellectuals but some are more instrumental to do work cooperatively. Groups learning collaboratively must have heterogeneity it implies that all the groups which carry out tasks cooperatively must consist of members having different ethnicity, religion, sex, personality class and language skills and determinations (Sabbah, 2016). Cooperative skills are incumbent to work in a group therefore such skills must be taught to the students because most of the students might lack these skills, the tendency to implement these skills as well as the language which is required to use in order to implement these skills (Bijani & Hashempour, 2020). When students carry out task in groups on the given tasks and they argue on their ideas and answers and when they incorporate collaborative skills into the tasks it helps to maximize the degree of group interaction (Huda, 2019).

Benefits of CL

There are various benefits of Cooperative learning technique on the outcome of the students working in a group in order to achieve mutual goals such as it helps to enhance students' knowledge and their desired outcome (Agussatriana, 2020).

Working cooperatively holds many positive aspects such as getting one a good leadership and decision-making skills (Dwigustini & Widiya, 2020). In any organisation or group, where students are working cooperatively in order to achieve their objectives, some tasks are needed to be functioned smoothly by incorporating cooperative learning techniques such as organizing work or obtaining common purposes, assisting team members, making sure the team members of a group achieve the target (Nikmah, 2020). By employing Cooperative learning technique, students having leadership qualities but not inclined to show it can be encouraged to prepare him for future leadership (Suryani & Rifa'at, 2019).

Challenges in CL

However, Cooperative learning techniques have many advantages for the students but most of the collaborative learning strategies introduced by the teachers in the classes do not have a positive impact on the students (Dwiniasih & Nugraha, 2019). For instance, in the United State of America, it is observed in elementary classes that students spend more than 90% of their time working individually or in large groups but less than 8% of time is devoted only to small groups instruction (Pianta et al. 2007). (Abrami et al. 2004) stated that hardly 16% of instructors employed collaborative learning techniques in their classes and the other 84% of teachers are not inclined to integrate cooperative based learning into their classes. Moreover, Students spend 65% of their time working individually, on the contrast 19% in group discussion and spend less than 13% of time on peer based discussion (Blatchford et al. 2003). Therefore, it is immensely significant to find out existen challenges which are involved in the utilization of collaborative learning techniques to be efficient to sort out more

smartly in the learning domains (Bijani & Hashempour, 2021).

Cooperative Learning Techniques

Cooperative learning is a type of teaching strategy that is used by classroom teachers to assist their pupils learn more rapidly by breaking them up into small groups to complete the job at hand (Sabbah, 2016). Every student is responsible for the accomplishment of the given assignment as well as to assist every individual included in the group to learn the knowledge quickly (Chandran & Shah, 2019). Collaborative learning is a guiding strategy where all the students included in the groups have to be divided into small groups by the teacher to carry out the task (Perkins, 1988). With the help of Cooperative learning techniques, the students are trained to achieve their goal in an environment which is likely to be more similar to the one which is going to be faced by them in their future practical life (Ghosh, 2012). Moreover, teachers involved in the process get the opportunity to work upon the basic abilities and on the soft and communication skills of the students that are precious for work and success in life of the students as well as upgrading them in the school academic context (Sakaeva & Ismagilova, 2017).

Jigsaw Technique

Jigsaw is a useful Cooperative learning technique which was invented in 1971, in Texas by a well-known person who was also a professor named Elliot Aronson (Adams 2013). Jigsaw is a student-Team based investigating activity which was invented by Elliot Aronson at a university of California and Texas in 1971 (Jaccob, 1998). Through Jigsaw technique students not only get the bigger picture but also understand their own section since they are supposed to test

individually (Mills & Cottel, 1998). It is a kind of activity in which each member of the group is given a section to be learnt and then it is the responsibility of that member to teach his section to all other members in order to get the bigger picture (Mills & Cottell, 1998). Jigsaw is a sort of cycling activity in which first of all groups are made then regrouping then students of the same sections come together in an expert group then group discussion and finally they are tested (Rolheiser & Stevahn, 1998). There are various types of collaborative learning techniques but Jigsaw is the most prominent of all of them in order to get the positive result (Kagan, 1994; Namaziandost, Nasri et al., 2019).

Think---Pair-Share Technique

Think-Pair-Share is a Cooperative learning technique which was first developed by Frank Lyman and his colleagues in 1981. Moreover, this technique consists of three different phases such as thinking phase which is an individual work, discussing phase which is a pairing work, and sharing phase which is a grouping work. Further, this technique is usually used in first language and also used in second language context. However, there are many Cooperative learning techniques but Think Pair Share (TPS) technique is deemed to be the most prominent strategy. Further, Think Pair Share (TPS) technique is created to help the learners who have a clear time and focus to establish ideas and then share it with the other students of the group. In this regard, Robertson claims that Think-pair-share is a sort of strategy which enables students to interact with the materials as well as the students in the group, not only this but also Think Pair Share technique helps the learners to acquire the content and develops interaction among the participants in the group and class (Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam

Negeri, 2016). In addition, it is worthwhile to investigate the contribution and effect of this strategy to improve students' accomplishment (Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam Negeri, 2016).

Round Robin

Round Robin is a kind of great structure as compared to that of where students have to answer individually like that on a paper or an answer sheet (Casanave, 1988). According to the Round Robin method each student of the group has to stand and discuss his part to the entire group and then the next student has to stand and tell his portion to the group and so on (Shih, 1992). Having been done with their respective parts, all the students in the group have to head together to further elaborate the topic until all the groups in the class have accomplished their tasks (Shih, 1992). To know whether the students in all groups have done or still they are in the process, just see that still students are standing to share their part or nobody is standing anymore (Paribakht & Wesche, 1993). However, the best way to effectively functionalize this method is to count the time given to each student by setting the timer. In this regard, one minute time will be set on the timer and then each student has to speak to fix one minute when that student has done his task then the next student will talk for one minute according to the time reset on the timer (Rhyn & van Staden, 2018).

Numbered Heads

Numbered heads is a very useful collaborating learning technique through which Numbered heads together in order to solve any difficult task with respect to academic learning (Hafsha, 2020). It is a very effective collaborative learning technique therefore teachers usually use this method to acquire positive results (Baskin & Shitai, 1996). In the process of Numbered Heads Together method students are given a fixed amount of

time to discuss their matters if they are prolonging the conversation the amount of time can be extended (Maryati & Sari, 2021). Therefore when the allotted time is up, the teacher gives the pupils a signal to turn their attention to him.

Team-Pair-Solo:

Team-Pair-Solo is a kind of collaborative learning method in which students first get together in order to solve the problem in a group, then they make pairs to further discuss the same task, finally they individually try to accomplish the task (Rosmiati & Nuryani, 2020). Therefore, it is believed and also this method gives the notion that people can carry out their tasks successfully when they work in a group as compared to working alone (Hudri & Irwandi, 2018). Moreover, students are capable of solving their problems alone provided that they first attempt to solve the same issue in collaboration with other students and then in a pair with any student in the group (Sembiring, 2022). Kangan (2000) states that Team Pair Solo is such a type of a Cooperative learning technique which can grow students' moral excellence because there are many kinds of virtues such as helpfulness, Cooperation, self-motivation, leadership and pride which can be developed with the help of this technique in any person's work (Sumiati et al., 2019).

Cooperative Learning and Reading Comprehension

Cooperative learning strategy is a process in which small groups of students work together in order to accomplish an assignment given by the teacher (Reynolds, 2015). Moreover, this assignment can be of reading, writing or any science related task in which students work together to do the assigned task. However, to enhance ESL students reading comprehension various types of Cooperative

learning strategies are used. In this regard, (Shih & Reynolds, 2015) used the Think-Pair-Share cooperative technique to determine whether its application in an EFL class has any beneficial effects on the students' reading comprehension. Additionally, the results demonstrated that the experimental group, which received instruction using the Think-pair-share technique, outperformed the control group, which received instruction in the conventional manner (Huang & Yang, 2015) revealed in their study that the utilization of cooperative learning strategy, explicit teaching before reciprocal teaching (ET-RT), has more convincing impacts over the direct instruction (DI) on the improvement of reading comprehension and motivations. Moreover, the study showed that the 36 low capacity students, taught by the teacher through ET-RT technique, performed well as compared to that of DI group.

Conceptual Framework of the Study.

Base on the forgoing literature the conceptual framework of the study is presented below:

Research Methodology

According to Schwardt (2007) research methodology is a procedure which shows that how an investigation should be carried out. Further, it includes analysis of procedures, principles and assumptions in a specific way

of investigation. As per, Creswell and Tashakkori (2007), Schwarzt (2007) point of view, methodology defines and formulates the types of problems which are indispensable to inquire.

Research Design

The term research design is determined as a procedure which is an integral means for research inquiry. Moreover, it involves many ways which are employed in a research work for the analysis and collection of data Schmidt (1999). Research design is the entire design for linking the abstractive research problems to the related and obtainable experimental research. Furthermore, it is an investigation that gives a particular way to process a research (Creswell, 2014).

With regard to this study, the researcher has used a quasi-experimental method to collect data. Moreover, quasi-experimental is a data collection method in which pre and post tests, of two different groups such as experimental and traditional group, are conducted before and after the treatment respectively. However, in this study a quasi-experimental data collection method has been employed. With respect to this, the researcher conducted a pretest of both the groups prior to the treatment and then a post test was conducted after the treatment.

Target Population and Sample

A population is defined as a group of people, objects, or other things. A sample of people who have some common and observable qualities can be taken. A population is also the complete group about which you want to draw conclusions.

Target Population

The present research study population has been taken from Computer Science (SC)

department from a Public Sector University in Karachi, Pakistan.

Sample

Various sampling techniques are there in the field of research and the nature of the suitability of the present research study. The purposive sampling technique was employed to select the sample from the target population. With respect to this, the researcher of this study has opted purposive sampling in order to get valid data from the participants.

Data Collection Methods

Multiple research methods have been introduced in the field of research domain, which are used in the research fields. Numerous methods have been employed in order to collect the required data to get the purpose of this study. That is why, the researcher of the present study, has collected the data through Pre-test and post-test.

Pre-test of ESL Reading Skills

The data were collected from 80 students of a public university in Karachi. With respect to this, a pre- test was conducted, prior to the treatment, by providing three IELTS reading comprehension passages to all the students participating in the test and each test consisted of 40 IELTS Mcqs. In this regard, the students were divided into two intact groups each consisting of 40 students. The purpose of the pretest was to know the reading comprehension level of the students before the treatment.

Post-test of Reading Skills

Having completed the reading comprehension treatment, the students' reading comprehension efficacy was tested again by conducting a post-test. The treatment consisted of 14 sessions and each session was

of 1 hour 30 minutes. However, for posttests too, an IELTS academic test was employed; each test consisted of 40 IELTS Mcqs. In this regard, the two intact groups, each having 40 students, were taught by employing an experimental and traditional way of teaching method.

Traditional Method of Teaching Reading

Traditional or conventional way of teaching is a technique or method of teaching in which the teacher plays an active role. On the contrary, students remain passive, which is also known as a conventional way of teaching. This type of teaching is still widely in use across the world. Moreover, the traditional way of teaching is a kind of teaching method in which students have to read and memorize the entire lesson one by one. Therefore, there is no cooperative activity taking place among the students because it is done individually.

Data Analysis Techniques

The research has used SPSS (V25) in order to analyze the collected data through independent and dependent sample t-tests.

Data Analysis

Standard statistical tools and procedures were used to conduct the statistical analysis for the current study. Subsequently completing the collection of data, collected data was processed and entered into a computer software for the persistence of analysis. A computer package for statistical data analysis (SPSS v.25) was utilized for the purpose of analysis of data. The foremost purpose of data analysis was to find out the answer of the research question. The findings of the pre-test scores and post-test scores for experimental and control groups were compared using descriptive and inferential statistics techniques. Among the tools of descriptive

statistics, mean and standard deviation were used to find out the pattern of the data. Hypothesis testing procedures such as the independent sample t-test and the paired sample t-test were used to test the data in order to determine the answer to the research question. Independent sample t-test was used to find out the significant difference between pre-test scores of control and experimental group and post-test scores of control and experimental group. In addition, paired sample t-test was used to find out the significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores of control group and pre-test and post-test scores of experimental group.

“If the Sig. value of the Shapiro-Wilk test is greater than 0.05, the data is normal. If it is below 0.05, the data significantly deviate from a normal distribution” (González-Estrada & Cosmes, 2019).

Table 4.1 Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statis tic	d f	Sig .	Statis tic	d f	Sig .
Experimental Group		4	.20		4	0.4
Pre-Test	0.108	0	0*	0.975	0	98
Experimental Group		4	0.0		4	0.2
Post-Test	0.144	0	36	0.967	0	93
Control Group		4	0.1		4	0.0
Pre-Test	0.115	0	98	0.952	0	85
Control Group		4	0.0		4	0.2
Post-Test	0.132	0	75	0.967	0	86

Findings of Research Question

The study posed the following research question 1:

RQ: What is the effect of cooperative learning techniques on ESL undergraduate university students' reading comprehension skills?

Comparison of control and experimental group pre-test scores

To compare the pre-test scores of control and experimental group researcher used independent sample t-test. A statistical method called the independent sample t-test that was used to compare the means of two independent groups. When using the independent samples t-test, the means of two samples taken from the same population could be identical. Independence of observations and the normality were the two main assumptions for independent sample t-test.

Table 4.2 Comparison for pre-test reading scores of control and experimental groups

Group Statistics					
Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Experimental Group	40	24.45	2.075	0.384	0.702
Control Group	40	24.25	2.560		

Table 4.2 presented the descriptive statistics for the pre-test reading scores of the experimental and control group. The mean (average) pre-test reading score for experimental group was 24.45 with standard deviation of 2.075, whereas the control group's mean pre-test reading score was 24.25 with standard deviation of 2.560. Furthermore, it contained the findings of the independent sample t-test. The p-value for the test statistic ($t = 0.384$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.702$) was listed in this table. Because the p-value

was higher than the 0.05 significance standard, it was not considered significant. As a consequence of this evidence, the researcher concluded that the experimental and control groups' pre-test reading scores were not statistically significantly dissimilar. Ere not statistically significantly dissimilar.

Comparison of pre-test and post-test scores of control group

To compare the pre-test and post-test scores of control group researcher used paired sample t-test. When each observation in one sample can be paired with an observation in the other sample, a paired samples t-test was used to compare the means of the two samples. When researcher was interested in the difference between two variables for the same subject, a paired t-test was used. These two variables were frequently separated in time. Statistics for pre-test and post-test reading scores of control group

Table 4.3 Comparison of pre-test and post-test scores of control group

Paired Samples Statistics					
	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Control Group Pre-Test	24.25	40	2.56		
Control Group Post-Test	25.20	40	2.937		
				-4.084	0.000

The descriptive statistics of the control groups' pre-test and post-test reading scores

was seen in Table 4.3. The mean pre-test reading score for the control group was 24.25 with standard deviation of 2.560, while the control group's mean post-test reading score was 25.20 with standard deviation of 2.937. Furthermore, the findings of the paired sample t-test for pre-test and post-test scores of control group were also listed in this Table. The test statistic value ($t = -4.048$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.000$).

As the p-value for the control group's pre-test and post-test reading scores ($p\text{-value} = 0.000$) was not higher than the standard significance level of 0.05, it was considered significant. As a result of this revelation, the researcher concluded that the control group's pre-test and post-test reading scores were statistically significantly different.

Comparison of pre-test and post-test scores of experimental groups

To compare the pre-test and post-test scores of experimental group researcher used paired sample t-test. When each observation in one sample can be paired with an observation in the other sample, a paired samples t-test was used to compare the means of the two samples. When researcher was interested in the difference between two variables for the same subject, a paired t-test was used. These two variables were frequently separated in time.

Table 4.4 Comparison for pre-test and post-test reading scores of experimental group

Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Experimental Group Pre-Test	24.45	40	2.075	-13.46	0.000

Experimental Group Post-Test	26.85	40	1.942	
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The descriptive statistics for pre-test and post-test reading scores of control group were presented in table 4.4. The mean pre-test reading score for the experimental group was 24.45 with standard deviation of 2.075, while the experimental group's mean post-test reading score was 26.85 with standard deviation of 1.94. Furthermore, the findings of the paired sample t-test for pre-test and post-test reading scores of experimental group were also listed in this Table. The test statistic value ($t = -13.46$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.000$). The As the p-value for the experimental group's pre-test and post-test reading scores ($p\text{-value} = 0.000$) was less than the standard significance level of 0.05, it was considered significant. As a result of this revelation, the researcher concluded that the experimental group's pre-test and post-test reading scores were statistically significantly different. However, descriptive statistics in table 4.4 provided the evidence that post-test reading scores of experimental group were higher than the pre-test reading scores of experimental group.

Comparison of control and experimental group post-test scores

To compare the pre-test scores of control and experimental group researcher used independent sample t-test. A statistical method called the independent sample t-test that was used to compare the means of two independent groups. When using the independent samples t-test, the means of two samples taken from the same population could be identical. Independence of observations and the normality were the two main assumptions for independent sample t-test.

Table 4.5 Comparison for post-test reading scores of control and experimental groups

Group Statistics					
Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Experimental Group	45	26.85	1.942	2.964	0.004
Control Group	40	25.20	2.937		

Table 4.5 illustrated descriptive statistics of experimental and control groups' reading scores in post-test. The mean post-test reading score of experimental group's was 26.85 with standard deviation of 1.942, while the control group's mean post-test reading score was 25.20 with standard deviation of 2.937. Furthermore, it contained the findings of the independent sample t-test. The p-value for the test statistic ($t = 2.964$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.004$) was listed in this table. Because the p-value was higher than the 0.05 significance standard, it was not considered significant. As a result of this finding, the researcher determined that the post-test reading scores of the control and experimental groups were statistically significantly dissimilar. However, descriptive statistics in this table provided evidence that post-test reading scores of the experimental group were higher than the post-test reading scores of the control group.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The answer of the research question is addressed in this final chapter. Moreover, the implications of the study, the limitations of study, recommendations for the future

research and the conclusion have been discussed accordingly.

Discussion of Key Findings

The core objective of the present study was to evaluate the impact of collaborative learning techniques on undergraduate students' reading comprehension skills. Therefore, two groups such as control and experimental were formed. Whereby, the control group was taught through traditional methods and the experimental group was taught via cooperative learning techniques. Later on the students' performance of both the groups were compared using pre and post tests.

Findings of Research Question

The research question of the study examined how cooperative learning techniques affected the reading comprehension skills of Pakistani undergraduate ESL students. The researcher concluded that there was no significant difference between the control and experimental groups' pre-test reading scores. It implies that prior to the treatment being administered to one of the groups, both of the ESL student groups were indistinguishable. Reading scores for the control groups pre- and post-tests were found different significantly, the researcher determined. It indicated that there was a difference between the control group's pre-test and post-test results. Since the traditional classroom teaching method was administered to the students in the control groups, their academic performance was found better before and after the treatment period. Moreover, the pre-test and post-test reading scores for the experimental group were statistically substantially different, showing that after using the cooperative learning technique, the experimental group's reading performance was determined to be improved. The descriptive statistics provided the evidence that the performance of the

learners improved more in cooperative learning technique than traditional classroom method. The post-test reading results of the experimental and control groups, however, were significantly different, demonstrating that when the cooperative learning technique was administered to one of the groups, the reading performance of the group receiving the treatment was observed to be better. With connection to this, the findings of this study are similar to the study of Sabbah (2016) who held a study to examine the effect of Cooperative learning strategy, Jigsaw strategy, on ESL students' comprehension of reading achievement. However, the result indicated that the control group was outperformed by the experimental group with respect to reading comprehension performance. On the contrary, the findings of this study are dissimilar to the study of Nejad and Keshavarzi (2015) who conducted a study to investigate the effects of cooperative learning technique Ask Together and Learn Together on reading comprehension of pre-university students. However, the result revealed that there was no significant difference between the control and experimental groups post-tests scores.

Implications of the Study

The present study has the following important implications for various stakeholders:

The study has found that the Jigsaw and Think-Pair-Share techniques are very useful for enhancing the ESL students' reading comprehension instead of using the traditional method.

Teachers need to create a positive learning environment and adopt the above mentioned approach in the class to improve their reading comprehension.

Think-Pair- Share approach with praise and incentives could be useful in developing ESL students' English reading comprehension.

Curriculum designers need to make reading comprehension an important part of curriculum and assessment. Students should be made part of the assessment, so that ESL students seriously focus on developing their reading comprehension skills.

Limitations of the Study

Following are mentioned some limitations of this study:

For the present study, the data was obtained from undergraduate ESL students only.

For the present study, the data was taken from government sector university's students only.

The researcher could only collect data from 80 participants only due to the time constraint.

Only quantitative tools were employed to study the reading comprehension skills.

Recommendations for Future Research

The recommendations for future research are given below:

The relationship of other important variables, such as inferring, activating, monitoring-clarifying, searching-selecting, questioning, summarizing, and visualizing-organizing can be explored in future research.

The Think-Pair- Share and Jigsaw could be explored through a qualitative study.

The present study was limited to Government Sector University in Karachi Pakistan, so in future the range of research can be extended to other provinces of Pakistan to assess ESL students' reading comprehension skills.

This study can also be done with school and college level students in future.

Conclusion

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of the Cooperative learning techniques on university ESL students' reading comprehension in the Pakistani context. The researcher concluded that there was no significant difference between the

experimental and control groups' pre-test reading scores. It implies that prior to the treatment being administered to one of the groups, both of the ESL student groups were indistinguishable. Reading scores for the control groups pre- and post-tests were found different significantly, the researcher determined. It indicated that there was a difference between the control group's pre-test and post-test results. Since the traditional classroom teaching method was administered to the students in the control groups, their academic performance was found better before and after the treatment period. Moreover, the pre-test and post-test reading scores for the experimental group were statistically substantially different, showing that after using the cooperative learning technique, the experimental group's reading performance was determined to be improved. The descriptive statistics provided the evidence that the performance of the learners improved more in cooperative learning technique than traditional classroom method. The post-test reading results of the experimental and control groups, however, were significantly different, demonstrating that when the collaborative learning technique was administered to one of the groups, the reading performance of the group receiving the treatment was observed to be better.

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